

CONSUMERS AWARENESS TOWARDS GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD AND GROCERY APPLICATIONS AND ITS IMPACT ON THE USAGE PATTERN

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Abstract

Recent advancements in the internet have accelerated the growth of online food and grocery services by enabling consumers to easily search for, compare, and access these services. Online ordering has completely revolutionized the food industry. Technology has a hidden impact on the business world, has revolutionized the restaurant business, and will keep doing a wonderful job. The culture of restaurants has been radically altered by a technologically advanced online meal ordering system, which also provides a whole new level of comfort for individuals all over the world. Everyone is in awe of the internet's ability to order food online and have groceries delivered, due to its ease and availability of food right away. Additionally, the ease of purchasing meals and groceries through a smartphone application or application program has undoubtedly taken some market share away from the tried-and-true "kirana" or mom-and-pop shops. The organized sector, as represented by several online businesses like Swiggy, Blink It, Zepto, and Big Basket, only accounts for 5-8 percent of the market share of the food and grocery industry, despite the fact that Asian countries have the sixth-largest grocery market in the world. The rise in the growth and development of online shopping of groceries and food has been seen immensely since the pandemic, however it has been flourishing way before that. One of the main reasons for the growth and rapid development in these applications is due to high attraction and interest of people towards it.

Keywords: Online Groceries, Food Applications, Mom-And-Pop Shops

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth in the industry of e-commerce have been seen in the past few years due to the advanced and emerging new technologies. E-commerce has brought a great advantage to E-tailing of groceries and food or in simple daily terms known as online ordering and delivering of groceries and food through the help of advanced mobile applications. According to the survey and graph derived from the source statista, this chart shows the growth of online grocery and food delivery sales through the use of mobile applications over the years. In financial year 2020, the online food delivery market value of platform to customer delivery in India was worth about 4.8 billion U.S. dollars. Owing to COVID-19 pandemic, this value was estimated to rise to 9.7 billion dollars in financial year 2025.

Graph showing the total Income estimated to be earned by the Delivering Industry

Source: www.Redseer.com

- This chart shows the online grocery shopping sales in India from the year 2016 to 2021 in billion us dollars.
- In the year 2016, the grocery market sales through apps were 0.3 billion US Dollars
- It tripled in more than just 4 years, by the end of 2020.
- By the end of 2025, the original figure of 2016 is to be seen going 5 to 6 times more and to reach to 9.7 billion US Dollars.

The rise in the growth and development of online shopping of groceries and food has been seen immensely since the covid 19 lockdown but it has been flourishing way before that. One of the main reasons for the seen growth and rapid development in these applications is due to high attraction and interest of people towards it. People are finding these applications very useful, as they provide easy product search and discovery and saves a lot of time, money and energy. Online food ordering and discovery platforms have transformed the way Indian customers eat.

REVIEW OF RESEARCH AND LITERATURE

Munshi, A & Singla, AR (2022): Exploring Key Growth Drivers and Strategies for Enhancing Performance of Indian Food /grocery Tech Startups. This paper explored the key growth drivers and challenges startup food tech platforms face and suggested strategies for enhancing their performance. They used a fully structured questionnaire to collect data from the delivery staff of startup food tech platforms in seven major cities in India and descriptive analysis was used based on the respondents' demographic information to find out the answers for the research. This study recommended innovative strategies that can make the food delivery business successful. The finding revealed that the key growth drivers included personalization &

focused marketing, quality assurance, extended convenience, and value to consumers, and their corresponding strategies were reconnoitered.

Vinish P, Prakash Pinto, Iqbal Thonse Hawaldar, Slima Pinto (2021): Antecedents of behavioral intention to use online food delivery services: an empirical investigation. The study aims to examine the antecedents of online food delivery leading to customer satisfaction and explore the recurring consumption occasions for ordering food online. The data was collected from 385 respondents through telephonic and mail survey using a structured questionnaire and was analyzed using multiple regression under buying motives, Demographic profile. The result of the study indicated a positive association between the constructs 'buying motives', 'aggregator attractiveness', and customer satisfaction. The variation in customers' satisfaction is largely attributable to the convenience of order placing, food quality, availability of food and restaurant reviews, offers and discounts, faster home delivery, and the wide choice of restaurants listed on the aggregator's website.

Preeti Kapuria and Harish S Nalawade (2021): Digitising Indian Retail: Analyzing Challenges and Exploring Growth Models. This aims at Acquiring new digitally savvy consumers is a major challenge for Kirana retailers and mainly to encourage small consumers to adopt digital technologies. It recommends that kiranas digitize through the 'phygital' (combining the physical with the digital), the use of Phygital and Convergence Models was taken into consideration for the analysis to be made. This paper analyses digitisation initiatives by the government, large e-commerce companies, and other private players, and identifies current concerns over technology adoption among kirana store proprietors.

Sufyan Habib and Nawaf N. Hamadneh (2021): Impact of Perceived Risk on Consumers Technology Acceptance in Online Grocery Adoption amid COVID-19 Pandemic. The study aims to identify the factors of customer's acceptance of technology in adaption of online grocery purchasing during the COVID-19 pandemic, to access the factors of consumer technology acceptance and its influence on online grocery purchasing. The research methodology used in this survey was that descriptive research made tools like regression analysis and Mediation Analysis were used to derive the results. This paper focuses on risk and consumer trust rather than these aspects. This study contributes a different perspective, considering how consumer acceptance of technology for online grocery shopping influences consumer trust and reduces the risk of online grocery.

Surendhranatha Reddy and Guru Basava Aradhya (2020): The title of the study: Driving Forces for the Success of Food Ordering and Delivery Apps: A Descriptive Study. The research objectives are to understand and identify driving forces for the success of online food order and delivery applications and also to develop a conceptual model to understand the dynamics of digital food/groceries delivery business. For research methodology purpose the secondary data from previous studies conducted on selected research problem. The researchers concluded that the research Marketers need to invest their resources cleverly as the competition in the segment also intensifying. Digital food delivery businesses can flourish in the future due to demographic and economic advantages in the market.

Need for and Significance of the Study

Food and groceries shopping is a part of daily life routine of a consumer, with the emergence of applications like online food and grocery deliveries has made a great impact on the life of all class people be it middle class or upper class. This study focuses on growth and impact of these applications on general public and to see the awareness of these applications among the people. The study intends to know the view of a normal consumer on these applications has changed their mindsets not only in the light of COVID- 19 but also post pandemic. The following study will understand the buying power of the users on this application, their needs and their understanding towards them.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main aim of the study is to realize the following:

1. To present the growth and development of Indian food and grocery applications and the impact it has made on the Indian economy; and
2. To analyze the level of awareness among the consumers towards food and grocery applications and its impact on the usage pattern of consumers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Primary data was collected by structured questionnaire consisting of questions on the opinions of consumers regarding the impact of these applications on their normal routine life. The secondary data was gathered from previous studies from various authenticated sources. The sample size was 151 responses. The data was processed using Ms. Excel and analyzed using SPSS software. Techniques such as simple average, cross tabulation, chi square and Anova were adopted.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Duration of usage by the respondent of the food and grocery delivery applications for online deliveries and the age of the respondent.

H0: There is no significance difference in association between usages of online delivery applications age of the respondent.

Table 1: Usage of online delivery Applications in association with Age

ANOVA					
Particulars	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.276	3	0.425	1.112	0.346
Within Groups	55.489	148	0.383		
Total	56.765	151			

Source: Primary Data

From the above table we see that the ANOVA test was performed where we get the F value as 1.112 and significant table value as 0.346. Therefore, since the F value is greater to the significant value, we reject the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant difference of association between Age and Usage of online Delivery Applications.

Association between how long do they think that the online food and delivery applications will retain their impact on the society and the age, Gender, profession of the respondent.

H0a: There is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and age of respondent.

H0b: There is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and gender of respondent.

H0c: There is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and profession of respondent.

Table 2: Retention of delivery applications impact in association with Age, Gender and Profession

		ANOVA				
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	1.276	3	0.425	1.112	0.346
	Within Groups	55.489	148	0.383		
	Total	56.765	151			
Gender	Between Groups	0.144	3	0.048	0.263	0.852
	Within Groups	26.407	148	0.182		
	Total	26.550	151			
Profession	Between Groups	1.625	3	0.542	0.501	0.682
	Within Groups	156.831	148	1.082		
	Total	158.456	151			

Source: Primary Data

H0a: There is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and age of respondent.

From the above table, we see that the ANOVA test was performed where we get the F value as 1.112 and significant table value as 0.346. Therefore, since the F value is greater to the significant value, we reject the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and age of respondent.

H0b: There is a significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and gender of respondent.

From the above following table, we see that the ANOVA test was performed where we get the F value as 0.263 and significant table value as 0.852. Therefore, since the F value is lower than the significant value, we accept the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the

society and gender of respondent.

H0c: There is a significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and profession of respondent.

From the above table, we see that the ANOVA test was performed where we get the F value as 0.501 and significant table value as 0.682. Therefore, since the F value is lower than the significant value, we accept the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant difference of association between retention of online delivery applications impact on the society and profession of respondent.

Preference in selecting food delivery and grocery delivery applications among the Gender and profession of the respondent.

H0a: There is no significance association between gender and profession and the preference of food delivery applications.

H0b: There is no significance association between gender and profession and the preference of grocery delivery applications.

Table 3: Preference of food and grocery delivery applications in association with Gender & Profession

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	0.449	3	0.150	0.822	0.484
	Within Groups	26.769	148	0.182		
	Total	27.219	151			
Profession	Between Groups	2.596	3	0.865	0.812	0.489
	Within Groups	156.742	148	1.066		
	Total	159.338	151			

Source: Primary Data

H0a: There is no significance association between gender and profession and the preference of food delivery applications

ANOVA test was performed where F value as 0.822 and significant table value as 0.484 for the variable Gender and F value as 0.812 and significant table value as 0.489 for variable Profession. Therefore, since the F value in both cases is greater than the significant value, we Reject the Null Hypothesis and conclude that there is no significance association between gender and profession and the preference of Food delivery applications.

Table 4: Preference of food delivery Applications in association with Gender, Profession

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	0.281	3	0.094	0.511	0.675
	Within Groups	26.937	148	0.183		
	Total	27.219	151			
Profession	Between Groups	6.358	3	2.119	2.036	0.111
	Within Groups	152.980	148	1.041		
	Total	159.338	151			

Source: Primary Data

H0b: There is no significance association between gender and profession and the preference of grocery delivery applications.

ANOVA test was performed where F value as 0.511 and significant table value as 0.675 for the variable Gender and F value as 2.036 and significant table value as 0.111 for variable Profession. Therefore, since the F value is less than the case of Gender but is higher in the case of Profession, we can conclude that we accept the Null Hypothesis there is no significance difference in association between gender and the preference of Food delivery applications where as in case of Profession since the F value is higher, we conclude that we reject the Null Hypothesis there is a significance difference in association between Profession and the preference of Food delivery applications.

Association between the income of the respondent and the average amount they spend on for online deliveries from these applications.

H0: There is no significance association between the income of the respondent and the average amount spent.

Table 5: Association between the income and the average amount spent

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.993 ^a	9	0.123
N of Valid Cases	151		

Ho: There is no association between the income of the respondent and the average amount spent.

Chi-Square Test value as 13.993 and from the table we get the critical value as 16.919. Therefore, since the value is lower than the Critical Value, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no association between the income of the respondent and the average amount spend by them.

Opinion on the changes due to these applications and the age and gender of the respondent.

Ho_a: There is no significance association between the age of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

Hob: There is no significance association between the gender of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

Table 6: Association between the opinion on the changes due to these applications and the Age of the respondent

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.486 ^a	4	0.241
N of Valid Cases	151		

H0_a: There is no significance association between the age of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

From the above table, we see that the Chi-Square Test was performed, where we get the Chi-Square value as 5.486 and from the table we get the critical value as 9.488. Therefore, since the Chi-Square value is lower than the Critical Value, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significance difference of association between the age of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

Table 7: Association between the opinion on the changes due to these applications and the Gender of the respondent

Chi-Square Tests			
Particulars	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.525 ^a	4	0.640
N of Valid Cases	151		

Hob: There is no significance association between the gender of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

From the above table we see that the Chi-Square Test was performed, where we get the Chi-Square value as 2.525 and from the table, we get the critical value as 9.488 accept. Therefore, since the Chi-Square value is lower than the Critical Value, we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significance difference of association between the Gender of the respondent and their opinion on the change due to these applications.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The Food and Grocery delivery service applications are gaining popularity in the recent times it is observed in the study that many have shifted from personally going to shop for groceries and food to depend upon these emerging delivery applications, which supports the growth of the industry in the recent times in India. Almost everyone in this era are familiar with these food and Grocery delivery service applications without any demographic constraint. In other

words, the food and grocery delivery applications such as Swiggy and Zepto have established their presence in almost everyone's mind in the day-to-day life of an individual. This indeed shows the impact the applications have made on the lives of the users, saying that it has simplified their lives for the better. The Indian customer's loyalty to any business depends on the quality of service provided by the company and price set by the applications. The majority of females has been seen as users of these applications indicating the progress of household independence in the nation. The industry is constantly growing on large scale and is expected to grow further more in the future leaving a good impact on the economy of the country and being a good welfare solution. The healthy competition between old applications and new emerging delivery applications is making the market even more interesting and providing its users with multiple options to choose from and new and better promotions and quality services to rely onto, altogether making it a good experience for the consumers.

There is still some untapped market left to be explored in sub urban and most of rural areas. Delivery Companies should try to expand their business there too. The Delivery companies should provide better communication options to the customers for better relations and their understanding. The Delivery companies should try to keep the prices of the food and groceries which are being delivered by them, as close as the present market value and not ending up exploiting their customers in the time of need.

Limitations: The sample size of the data collected is limited to only 151 responses based on the questionnaire which is collected through random sampling method. The study is confined to the city of Hyderabad only. The study needs to enhance the usage of other statistical measures in order to get a better view of the analysis

Scope for Further Research: Present research had focused on limited number of customers; it can be further done on a larger sample so as to get more verified responses. Focus can be on exploring the demographic profile and its impact.

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